

ITAP Spring Seminar (2023)- June, 16, 2023

Teaching the Pragmatics of Emotions

**Fostering Students' Emotional Engagement in Higher Education:
Exploiting Multimodal Materials Pragmatically**

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INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION
FOR TEACHING PRAGMATICS

ITAP Spring Seminar **Teaching the pragmatics of emotions**

June 16, 2023 9:25 - 17:30 (CET)

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9:25 - 9:30

9:30 - 10:30

10:30 - 11:00

11:00 - 11:30

11:30 - 13:30

Welcome

Plenary Lecture

Jean Marc Dewaele Birkbeck, University of London, UK

Teaching emotion words in a foreign language merely scratches the surface.

Workshop

Elisabet Comelles Pujadas and Natalia Judith Laso Martín

Universitat de Barcelona, Spain

Using AntConc to increase students' motivation through pragmatic exploitation of materials: a corpus-based analysis of Emily in Paris.

Coffee break

Individual presentations

Consuelo Montes-Granado Universidad de Salamanca, Spain

*Fostering students' emotional engagement in Higher education:
Exploiting multimodal materials pragmatically.*

This paper reports on an **innovative teaching design** for a Pragmatics course at university level, using multimodal materials, and analysing them from a pragmatic perspective.

Aim: to foster students' emotional and cognitive engagement while learning pragmatic competence

- in line with instructional design research

- in line with action research

- in line with the latest trends in Pragmatics

J. Culpeper, M. Gillings. (2019). Pragmatics: Data Trends. *Journal of Pragmatics*.

Highlights

- Pragmatics continues to be strongly linked to data, especially “real” data.
- Pragmatics is shifting its analytical focus towards more macro, contextual units.
- Pragmatics is engaging datasets of increasing size, though still avoids the very largest corpora.
- Pragmatics is less dominated by purely spoken data, increasingly using multimodal data and digital media data, though the use of more interactive, dialogic data is increasing.
- Pragmatics continues to diversify the range of languages it treats.

These authors also added:

Utterances, as the focal point of analysis, have declined quite considerably (p.7)

genre is undergoing a gentle increase

In this innovative design, I have chosen the genre of TV advertising

due to its multimodal nature

I have used adverts both in Spanish and in English

Adverts: a multimodal genere

Adverts have been chosen as an interesting genre of multimodal materials to illustrate pragmatic concepts. Even though adverts are complex pieces of persuasive communication, their multimodal nature is very alluring to students.

The hypothesis was that using these materials will enhance student motivation.

More reasons for choosing the genre of advertising

- part of our daily life
- its multimodal nature: alluring
- advertisers exploit all types of semiotic resources (Montes Granado, 2022):

adverts: interesting materials for a Pragmatics course
(to be exploited emotionally)

- **strategy to enhance students' motivation to learn Pragmatics**
- **at the same time as improving their critical thinking skills**

In relation to Multimodality

Communication is multimodal. Meaning is not conveyed through one means—or mode—only, but through a multiplicity of modes working together (Kress and van Leeuwen, 2001).

Multimodality is considered as a phenomenon of contemporary communication (Adami, 2016)

Grapin (2019) promoted an expanded view of meaning-making in content areas by articulating disciplinary practices that are inherently multimodal. (Also see Thompson, 2008; and Yi & Angay-Crowder (2016)

As in this innovative design for the course of Pragmatics

Aim: engage students emotionally in their understanding of pragmatic concepts: exploiting materials emotionally

Analytical perspective: adverts as microcosms

as deceitful microcosms

that can be deconstructed thanks to pragmatic conceptual frameworks

Important concept in publicity: **BRANDING**

Branding: emotional association with the brand name

Tools to explain (to deconstruct) Branding:

pragmatic concepts from a Multimodal perspective

Methodology

Participants: 110 university students enrolled in the Pragmatics course for the Degree in English Studies (Universidad de Salamanca). This is a compulsory course, organised in three groups, in the fourth year of the Degree.

Students were divided into teams of around 12 or 14 members

Methodology

In order to facilitate a positive attitude the following strategies were followed:

- These groups were self-created (although respecting the average size of around 12 or 14 members)
- Each team chose the advert they will analyse, but with the guidelines and supervision of the educator (some adverts were more appropriate than others)
- Criteria followed to choose the advert: adverts from strong companies because their marketing campaigns are very subtle and persuasive

Timing:

- 1) In the first stage of the course (the first 7 or 8 weeks) they were taught pragmatic concepts by the educator, who used a range of adverts to illustrate concepts
- 2) The remaining weeks were devoted to the students' group projects to deconstruct an advert

this process was monitored by the educator:

tutorial sessions for each team

A wide-angle photograph of a sunset over the ocean. The sky transitions from a pale yellow at the top to a soft pink and purple near the horizon. The water is a deep blue with gentle ripples. In the foreground, a small wave with white foam washes onto a sandy beach.

illustration

the advert of a famous soft drink

A sunset over the ocean with a sandy beach in the foreground. The sky is a mix of orange, pink, and purple, transitioning into a blue sea. The beach is visible at the bottom of the frame.

What is being communicated here?

What illocutionary forces are communicated through the semiotic resources (multimodal meaning making) in the advert?

emotions — SHARED youth identity

these illocutionary forces = involvement politeness

Emotions:

Youth identity - being equal, being peers

The Solidarity Axe = being in control

magic = the discourse of happiness

Involvement politeness: closeness, rapport, friendliness, a sense of shared identity

to redress the potential sense of imposition of any advert (POLITENESS AS MITIGATION)

Another level of analysis: Confrontation with the level of reality

Power axe

marketing professionals are in control: they create adverts to cause in potential consumers:

a willing suspension of disbelief (as in fiction)

consumers perceive the advert as a reflection of reality

the advert = a multimodal microcosm (of emotions)

A gathering of friends: being equal, peers,
welcoming, young people

Open space (informal American household)

Inclusive: intercultural, races, gender

final logo: my recipe for magic:

the discourse of happiness: pasta + soft drink

Hidden illocutionary force: matching these emotions with the brand name = **Branding (emotional, not rational)**

Relevance Theory (Wilson & Carston, 2019)

the advert = the explicature

The advert as a contrived explicature

Created with multimodal resources (not only the verbal language): very alluring

a process of covert communication (Relevance theory)

only some implicatures are activated: appealing to emotions

other potential implicatures are diverted from our attention

Implicatures in the advert:

A sense of SHARED youth identity: being equal, being peers

= The Solidarity Axe

+

= Being in control

= magic = the discourse of happiness

Implicatures retrieved with low processing effort (multimodal nature) and having high cognitive effects = very high relevance)

Deconstructing this advert

hidden implicatures: **ignored in the interpretative process of the advert**

rational, real life negative implicatures (health issues)

are diverted from the microcosm

diverted from the focus of rational awareness

the advert = a process of covert communication:

the interpretative path is short-sighted, loaded with emotions

this deconstruction impacts students: emotional engagement

Ways to assess the impact of this design on students:

1) through observation during the process:

the educator monitors the process of each team, providing each team with a tutorial session that usually lasted two hours or more.

MY DESIGN is articulated around a test and a group project, applying all the concepts to deconstruct persuasion in publicity. Would you hav... memory, instead? Please choose your preference.

63 respuestas

- The design as it is now (a test + a group project)
- A final exam (with no group project)

GROUP PROJECT. This has been my strategy to facilitate your participation as well as your learning.
Please tell me your degree of appreciation for this practice.

63 respuestas

ASSESSMENT SESSIONS: this has been an important strategy that I have implemented to facilitate your learning of the concepts and to solve any kind...s been my intention. Have they been useful to you?

63 respuestas

My aim has been to foster in you the skill of critical thinking in reference to persuasion in publicity.
In your opinion, is this an interesting skill to train or is it better not to waste time with this?

63 respuestas

- Yes, it can be a useful skill
- No, it is better not to waste time with that

Students' opinions in their reflective feedback

They highlight that this teaching design has been not only

innovative and rewarding for them, but very **relevant to their daily reality**

They are **grateful for having developed critical thinking skills**

for having improved their **pragmatic competence** & their **multimodal literacy**

Concluding remarks

- **Very positive outcomes of this teaching approach:**

student emotional and cognitive engagement: **pedagogy of learning by doing**

student appreciation of the usefulness of pragmatic conceptual frameworks to understand communication, and persuasive communication in publicity in particular

Their motivation to deconstruct an advert, applying pragmatic concepts, is very high

- **Challenge:**

the ability to apply pragmatic concepts by students is not easy:

it requires the educator monitoring each group project and helping them during the process.

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Acknowledgement:

Grant PID2021-122465NB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 and by “ERDF A way of making Europe”.

A photograph of a grassy area with two tree trunks and long shadows cast across the lawn. The grass is green and well-maintained. The shadows are long and dark, indicating it is either early morning or late afternoon. There are some fallen leaves and twigs scattered on the grass. In the background, there are some large rocks and more trees.

Thank you

photos © Consuelo Montes Granado